

Predictors of licensure examination for teachers' performance

Balinario, Jick C.¹, Ofqueria, Mary Grace M.², Arca, Lina B.³

^{1,2,3}College of Education, Northern Negros State College of Science and Technology, Philippines

Corresponding email: jcbalinario@nonescost.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

The study employed a descriptive correlational research design, in which the graduates' academic performance and other factors that significantly predicted their LET performance were examined from the Academic Year 2016-2018. Respondents were randomly selected from a list of NONESCOST LET takers requested from the Professional Regulatory Commission, with a total of 175 respondents identified in this study. The data were analyzed using percentages, means, standard deviations, t-tests, Pearson r, and linear regression analysis. The results revealed that LET takers have difficulty passing the specialization areas in the Licensure examination for teachers. BSEd graduates perform better in the three areas of the exam than non-BSEd graduates. High scholastic ratings and passing admission scores have a better performance in the Licensure examination. Likewise, there was a significant difference between the age, mothers' educational attainment, course, GPA, and admission entrance score, and no significant difference in civil status, father's educational attainment, and type of school to the LET performance of respondents. There is a significant indirect relationship between the profile of the respondents such as age, course, Entrance Exam, and Grade point average. Lastly, the respondent's mother's educational attainment, course, GPA, and entrance examination are significant predictors of LET performance. It is recommended the college will concentrate on the area of specialization in the conduct of review classes and strengthen the college-wide admission and retention policy. Non-education graduates who wish to take education units should be given priority to be admitted to the college's post-undergraduate program and given enough seminars and review classes.

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INTRODUCTION

The Philippine education system strives to provide quality education, foster critical thinking, and develop well-rounded individuals capable of contributing to the advancement of the country and actively participating in the global community. The Philippine government prioritized the education sector which usually received the largest share of the national budget. The Philippine government supported several educational reforms and mechanisms to be put in place to guarantee the quality of education provided by higher learning institutions. Philippine Regulation Commission monitors school performance in licensure examinations under R.A. 8981. Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) is one of the mechanisms to measure the performance of Higher Learning Institutions offering Teacher Education programs (Visco, 2015). Likewise, Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCUP) requires a 25% increase from the National passing rate in the Board Examination rating to be qualified for the higher level of accreditation. One of the indicators that a LET taker has mastered the LET competencies is passing the Teachers Licensure Examination.

As stipulated in CMO No. 80, series of 2017, Teacher Education Institutions must have in place selective admission policy for Teacher Education Programs. Northern Negros State College of Science and Technology as a Teacher Education Institution implemented already its selective admission for several years but its performance in the LET is still low. In March and September 2016, the college passing rate was 25% and 22.56%, respectively, compared to the national passing rate of 35.43% and 33.78%. In March and September 2017, the college passing rate was 16.67% and 22.22%, respectively, versus the national passing rate of 25.46% and 46.37%. In March and September 2018, the college passing rate was 54.55% and 18.52%, respectively, compared to the national passing rate of 48.03% and 29.91%. To summarize the results, college passing rates were lower than national passing rates, indicating poor performance in the teacher licensure examination.

NONESCOST as a Teacher Education Institution looks for ways to improve its performance in the LET. Several measures had been adopted such as implementing its admission and retention policy, curriculum revision based on CHED Policies, Standards, and Guidelines as well as conducting LET in-house review for free among its graduates planning to take the LET. According to Ventayen, 2020, the attendance of students in LET reviews contributed significant results to the overall performance of the institution.

According to Ofqueria (2020), the college's poor performance on the LET can be attributed to the non-education takers whose performance is low in general, professional, and specialization. The low performance in the 3 areas could mean that LET takers were not able to master competencies in the LET. The college typically has non-education graduate students who consistently contributed very low results in the licensure examination for teachers. The purpose of this study is to better understand how to make predictions about the results of teacher licensure examinations. Researchers wanted to know if factors like age, civil status, parental educational attainment, type of school attended, GPA, and entrance exam results influenced LET performance.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to determine the predictors of LEPT performance of NONESCOST LEPT takers from the Academic year 2016-2018, specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. 1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of the following;
 - a. Age
 - b. Civil Status
 - c. Educational Attainment of Parents
 - d. Course
 - e. Type of School Graduated
 - f. General Point Average (GPA)
 - g. Entrance Exam Result

2. What is the LET performance in General, Professional, specialization, and overall LET ratings in terms of profile respondents?
3. Is there a significant difference between the LET performance rating of the respondents according to their profiles?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the admission profile to the LET performance rating of the respondents?
5. Is there a significant predictor of LET Performance using the profile of the respondents such as Age, Civil Status, Educational Attainment of Parents, Course, Type of School Graduated, GPA, and Entrance Exam Result?

Hypotheses of the Study:

- Ho: There is no significant difference between the LET performance rating of the respondents according to their profile?
- Ho: There is no significant relationship between the admission profile and the LET performance rating of the respondents?
- Ho: There is no significant predictor of LET Performance using the profile of the respondents such as Age, Civil Status, Educational Attainment of Parents, Course, Type of School Graduated, GPA, and Entrance Exam Result.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study employed a descriptive correlational research design, in which the graduates' academic performance and other factors that significantly predicted their LET performance were examined. The study was conducted at Northern Negros State College of Science and Technology, Old Sagay, Sagay City. The respondents of the study were graduates of Northern Negros State College of Science and Technology from AY 2016-2018. These were the graduates from BSEd and other program graduates who took 18 units in education from other TEIs or finish a Certificate in Teaching or Diploma in Teaching. This study employed simple random sampling to make generalizations about a population, where the respondent's population has an equal chance of being chosen. The respondents were selected by chance but with a known probability of selection. Respondents were randomly selected from the list of NONESCOST LET takers requested by the Professional Regulatory Commission from AY 2016-2018. A total of 175 respondents were identified in this study as the sample size. The study used secondary data, data on LET rating were requested from PRC Manila. Entrance exam results of students were taken from the College Guidance Center of NONESCOST while other related data identified in the admission profile of students were downloaded from the College Students' Information and Accounting System (SIAS) through the approval of the College Data Privacy Officer. The admission profile of students was analyzed using frequency and percentage. Mean was also used to calculate scores, and the results were interpreted in the same way as the standards used for the licensure examination. The T-test was used to determine whether there were any significant differences between variables and Pearson-r correlation analysis was used to test the association of LET scores with academic, college admission, and other variables whose results were interpreted. Similarly, linear regression analysis was used to determine the predictors' contributed variation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation of the discussion is according to the order of the statement of the problem. There were 175 respondents selected randomly. Table 1 showed the profile of LET takers in terms of the following; Age, Civil Status, Educational Attainment of Parents, Course, Type of School Graduated, GPA, and Entrance Exam Result. Data

revealed that 55.4% of LET takers fall under the age range of 18-24 which is a normal age for college students. As to the educational attainment of the father, only 8% are college graduates, 27.4% did not finish their secondary education, and 11.4% did not finish their elementary schooling. For mothers' educational attainment, 8.6% are college graduates, 23.4% are at the high school level, and 4.6% did not finish elementary education. This was supported by developmental psychology models, the model of investment and family stress, which is used to lay the groundwork for an evaluation of research linking parents and parenting to schooling and academic achievement, (Simons, et.al, 2016). When interpreting studies on the effects of parents and parenting on children's education and academic performance, these theoretical models emphasize the importance of taking into account related stresses such as poverty, parent social, and cultural views, values, and racism. Parental involvement in education and learning is strongly linked to higher academic performance throughout infancy and adolescence (Brotman et al., 2018).

Table 1: Admission profile of the Respondents (n=175)

Profile of Respondents		Frequency	Percent
Age	15-17 yrs. old	67	38.3
	18-24 yrs. old	97	55.4
	25-34 yrs. old	9	5.1
	35-up yrs. old	2	1.1
Father Educational Attainment	Elem. Level	20	11.4
	Elem. Grad.	36	20.6
Mother Educational Attainment	High Sch. Level	48	27.4
	High Grad	38	21.7
	College Level	19	10.9
	College Grad.	14	8.0
Course	Elem. Level	8	4.6
	Elem. Grad.	34	19.4
	High Sch. Level	41	23.4
	High Grad	49	28.0
Type of School	College Level	28	16.0
	College Grad.	15	8.6
Civil Status	BSED Graduate	122	69.7
	Non-BSED Graduate	53	30.3
GPA	Public	145	82.9
	Private	30	17.1
Entrance Exam	Single	166	94.9
	Married	9	5.1
	1-1.5	12	6.9
	1.6-2.0	105	60.0
TOTAL	2.0-2.5	56	32.0
	2.6-3.0	2	1.1
	1-1.5	12	6.9
	Above 45	106	60.6
	Below 45	69	39.4
TOTAL		175	100.0

Furthermore, more than half of the respondents are graduates of the BSEd program which is 69.7% while 30.3% graduated from a non-education program offered by the College. These graduates took units in education from other Teacher Education Institutions and were qualified to take the LET. Most of the respondents finished their

secondary education in a public school comprised of 82.9% while in private schools only 17.1 %. In terms of the civil status majority of the respondents are single comprised of 94.9% while married status is only 5.1%. For GPA, 60% of the respondents have a GPA of 1.6 to 2.0 which in the NONESCOST grading system as stipulated in the Students' Handbook is interpreted as Very Good/Above average academic performance. Lastly, in terms of the entrance exam result as an admission requirement majority got a score of 45 above which belongs to stanine 4 and up, and only 39.4 % got a score below 45 which belongs to stanine 3 and below. The admission test is an important predictor of licensure examination success. This confirmed that poor performance on the admission test is related to a low licensure examination passing rate (Nool et al., 2017).

Table 2: LET performance in general, professional, specialization, and overall LET ratings in terms of profile respondents (n=175)

Profile of Respondents		Gen. Education				Prof. Ed.			Specialization			Overall Performance		
		N	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
Age	Age 15-17	67	83.73	4.69	P	78.97	5.48	P	73.59	8.83	F	77.97	6.04	P
	Age 18-24	97	77.77	8.85	P	72.16	9.94	F	68.36	9.46	F	71.74	8.51	F
	Age 25-34	9	76.11	10.15	P	69.22	13.59	F	63.66	11.80	F	68.96	11.14	F
	Age 35-up	2	70.50	14.85	F	78.00	4.24	P	74.50	3.53	F	77.70	2.40	P
Father Educational Attainment	Elem. Level	20	79.95	7.38	P	75.60	5.98	P	67.05	9.32	F	73.41	6.48	F
	Elem. Grad.	36	80.58	7.45	P	75.44	9.57	P	72.86	9.35	F	76.08	8.27	P
	High Sch. Level	48	78.62	9.85	P	74.17	9.45	F	70.58	9.92	F	73.05	9.11	F
	High Grad	38	80.60	8.25	P	74.66	10.91	F	70.63	9.00	F	74.41	8.66	F
	College Level	19	80.26	7.45	P	75.89	8.09	P	69.37	10.32	F	74.08	8.31	F
	College Grad.	14	79.86	6.58	P	71.64	9.71	F	66.42	10.56	F	72.17	7.79	F
Mother Educational Attainment	Elem. Level	8	82.87	6.31	P	77.37	6.90	P	72.12	8.84	F	77.22	5.96	P
	Elem. Grad.	34	79.53	6.90	P	74.52	9.15	F	73.35	7.36	F	75.29	7.23	P
	High Sch. Level	41	76.88	9.70	P	71.63	10.66	F	66.92	10.17	F	71.07	9.37	F
	High Grad	49	80.69	8.96	P	76.12	8.47	P	71.65	9.27	F	75.31	7.95	P
	College Level	28	82.82	5.86	P	77.60	7.78	P	69.75	10.45	F	75.77	7.61	P
	College Grad.	15	79.20	6.55	P	71.80	10.24	F	67.00	11.27	F	70.40	9.29	F
Course	BSED Graduate	122	83.43	4.76	P	78.73	4.99	P	72.44	8.05	F	77.22	5.52	P
	Non-BSED Graduate	53	71.74	8.70	F	65.38	10.28	F	65.01	11.18	F	66.76	9.23	F
Type of School	Public	145	79.48	8.51	P	74.24	9.78	F	69.96	10.06	F	73.75	8.66	F
	Private	30	81.87	6.31	P	76.83	6.31	P	71.30	7.80	F	75.49	6.64	P
Civil Status	Single	166	79.89	8.37	P	74.71	9.29	F	70.47	9.45	F	74.19	8.32	F
	Married	9	79.78	4.65	P	74.22	10.34	F	65.11	13.29	F	71.53	9.10	F
GPA	1-1.5	12	87.00	3.33	P	82.17	4.50	P	80.08	4.73	P	82.68	2.13	P
	1.6-2.0	105	81.31	7.16	P	76.96	7.45	P	71.98	8.03	F	76.02	6.87	P
	2.0-2.5	56	76.12	8.51	P	69.55	9.90	F	65.26	10.52	F	68.99	8.39	F
	2.6-3.0	2	67.50	19.09	F	54.00	12.72	F	55.00	2.82	F	60.50	14.84	F
Entrance Exam	Above 45	106	83.84	4.51	P	79.01	5.00	P	74.30	7.25	F	78.28	4.91	P
	Below 45	69	73.79	8.89	F	68.02	10.45	F	63.88	9.64	F	67.55	8.41	F
TOTAL		175	79.88	8.21	P	74.68	9.31	F	70.19	9.70	F	74.05	8.36	F

Legend: 75 and Above Passed (P); below 75 Failed (F)

Table 2 showed that LET takers performed according to the profile of the respondents and categories to the 3 major areas in LET as a whole, the results reflected that the majority passed in general education with a mean score of 79.88 with a variance of 8.21 which is interpreted as passed, for professional education 74.69 with a variance of

9.31 which is interpreted as almost passed and for specialization 70.19 with the variance of 9.70 and for the average is 74 .05 with a variance of 8.36 rating which is interpreted as failure. This implies that those takers of LET have difficulty passing the area of specialization and almost passed in professional education.

In terms of age, younger Ages 15-17 have an overall rating in LET (M=77.97, SD=6.04) with a passing remark. For age, Ages 18-24 have an overall remark of (M=71.74, SD=8.51) failed, Ages 25-34 have an overall remark of (M=68.96, SD=11.14) failed and lastly age 35-up have an overall remark of passed (M=77.70, SD=2.40). This showed that Younger age and older ages performed well in the Licensure examination of teachers.

For educational attainment, Father's educational attainment in Elementary graduate has an overall rating of passed (M=76.08, SD=8.27) and the rest attainment got a failed score in the LET. Mothers with educational attainment graduate of Elementary, Graduate of High School, and College Level received LET remarks (M=75.29, SD=7.23; M=75.31, SD=7.95; M=75.77, SD=7.61, respectively), while the rest received a failed score.

Table 2 also showed that BSEd graduates have a passed result in the 3 major areas which are 83.43 for General Education, 78.73 for Professional Education, 72.44 for specialization, and 77.73 overall rating which is interpreted as passed when compared to non-education graduates 71.74, 65.38, 65.01, 66.75 overall ratings which are interpreted as failed, respectively. This below-passing non-BSEd graduates' performance can be attributed to the lack of mastery of competencies and lack of preparation for the licensure examination on the part of the LET takers. This finding can be supported by a study conducted by Ofqueria (2020), where the lack of mastery in the 3 areas in general, professional, and specialization in the examination will lead to a failing performance.

For the type of school of the respondents showed that respondents who graduated from private high schools got an overall passing remark (M=75.49, SD=6.64), but for public high schools their LET remarks failed (M=73.75, SD=8.66). Furthermore, the civil status of respondents single and married have an overall remark of failed in the LET (M=74.19, SD=8.32 and M=71.53, SD=9.10, respectively). Married individuals have lower performance in LET than those single. It was supported that married undergraduate students adapted to numerous responsibilities with varying degrees of success (Mudhovozi, 2011). Balancing home and college life was a major challenge. To deal with the competing roles, the students said they used time management skills.

Lastly, for General Point Average (GPA), respondents with a GPA of 1.0-1.5 and 1.6-2.0 have an overall rating of passed (M=82.68, SD=2.13; M=76.02, SD=6.87 respectively), while GPA of 2.0-2.5 and 2.5-3.0 has an overall rating of failed (M=68.99, SD=8.39; M=60.50, SD=14.84). This implies that respondents who have a higher GPA score will most likely to passed the LET. The College entrance exam complied with the College Admission Policy requirement as reflected in the admission score or entrance examination results of students which have a mean score of 83.84 for General Education, 79.01 for professional Education, and 74.30 for specialization while the non-BSEd falls below the required admission of the College for entrance examination which means a score of 73.79 for General Education, 68.02 for professional Education and 63.88 for specialization. The below admission score is indicative that they fall short of the College of Education Admission policy. According to Valencia (2020), the higher the IQ the greater chances of passing the examination.

Table 3 revealed a statistically significant difference between the age, mothers' educational attainment, course, GPA, and admission entrance score to the LET performance of NONESCOST LET takers from AY 2016-2018 with the p-value lower than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.00, 0.029, 0.00, 0.00, \text{ and } 0.00$, respectively) as a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. Likewise, there was no significant difference between the civil status, educational attainment of the father, and school type to the LET performance of NONESCOST LET takers from AY 2016-2018 with the p-value greater than 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.354, 0.598, \text{ and } 0.303$, respectively) as a result, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Table 3: Comparison of LET performance rating and respondents according to its profile (n=175)

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PRCRating * Age	Between Groups	(Combined)	1808.188	3	602.729	9.951	.000
	Within Groups		10357.044	171	60.568		
	Total		12165.232	174			
PRCRating * CivilStatus	Between Groups	(Combined)	60.353	1	60.353	.863	.354
	Within Groups		12104.880	173	69.970		
	Total		12165.232	174			
PRCRating * FatherEdAttain ment	Between Groups	(Combined)	259.013	5	51.803	.735	.598
	Within Groups		11906.219	169	70.451		
	Total		12165.232	174			
PRCRating * MotherEdAttai nment	Between Groups	(Combined)	857.657	5	171.531	2.564	.029
	Within Groups		11307.575	169	66.909		
	Total		12165.232	174			
PRCRating * Course	Between Groups	(Combined)	4043.767	1	4043.767	86.139	.000
	Within Groups		8121.466	173	46.945		
	Total		12165.232	174			
PRCRating * TypeofSch	Between Groups	(Combined)	74.514	1	74.514	1.066	.303
	Within Groups		12090.719	173	69.889		
	Total		12165.232	174			
PRCRating * GPA	Between Groups	(Combined)	3101.636	3	1033.879	19.506	.000
	Within Groups		9063.597	171	53.003		
	Total		12165.232	174			
PRCRating * EntranceExam	Between Groups	(Combined)	4811.294	1	4811.294	113.185	.000
	Within Groups		7353.938	173	42.508		
	Total		12165.232	174			

There is a significant difference in age to the performance in LET of Respondents with an alpha value of 0.000. Aged 15-17 and age 35-up have a comparable results because they perform well in the exam (M=77.97, SD=6.04 and M=77.70, SD=2.40). Age 18-24 and age 25-34 have comparable results but they do not perform well (M=68.96, SD=11.14 and M=77.70, SD=2.40). The data supports that younger and older ages perform well than those in middle age in the teacher's licensure examination which explains that age is in direct opposition to LET

performance. In comparison to older reviewers, younger reviewers or those taking the LET for the first time have a higher chance of passing (Corpuz et al, 2014).

For educational attainment, there is a significant difference for mother educational attainment with an alpha value of 0.029, in which Elementary graduate, High School Graduate, and College Level have comparable results in LET (M=75.29, SD=7.23; M=75.31, SD=7.95; M=75.77, SD=7.61, respectively) compared to Elem. Level, High Sch. Level, and College Graduate. This implies that respondents with College level mother parents have high results in LET compared to other educational levels of parents. Furthermore, there is no significant difference in fathers' educational attainment on LET performance which implies that regardless of fathers' attainment it has no direct effect on the performance in LET.

The course has a significant difference in the performance of LET takers with an alpha value of 0.00. BSED graduates showed a higher performance (M=77.22, SD=5.52) compared to non-education graduates (M=66.76, SD=9.23). The huge discrepancy in performance between the two (2) groups in professional education is supported by Laganao's (2017) study, which indicated that education takers struggled in the Professional Education portion. If education LET takers struggle in this area due to their 51 Professional Education units, non-educational takers would probably struggle even more since they only have 18 education units, which already qualify them to take the teacher's board exam according to Republic Act 7836. Curriculum specialists and others participating in teacher education programs, especially BSEd programs, must consider this. As a result, Delos Angeles (2019) supports the low pass rate of non-education in professional education by claiming that insufficient exposure and preparation during pre-service education may play a role in poor performance.

GPA has a significant difference to the performance of LET of NONESCOST LET takers with an alpha value of 0.00. It was noted that GPAs of 1.0-1.5 and 1.6-2.0 have comparable results in their performance but GPA 1.0-1.5 got the higher performance (M=82.68, SD=2.13; M=76.02, SD=6.87 respectively). Likewise, those with a GPA of 2.0 and below have very low performance in LET (M=68.99, SD=8.39; M=60.50, SD=14.84). It revealed that a higher scholastic rating also tends to have higher performance in the teacher's Licensure examination. Furthermore, studies show that students with a lower GPA are more likely to score poorly on the Teacher Licensure Examination. Several studies have found that college significant predictor of LET scores is GPA (Ballado et. al, 2014; Chan-Rabanal, 2016; Puertos, 2015; Kalaw, 2015; Ballado, et al., 2018).

There was a significant difference between the admission score and the performance in LET of the respondents with an alpha value of 0.00. Respondents with a score of 40 above got a higher performance (M=78.28, SD=4.91) as compared to those below 40 admission score (M=67.55, SD=8.41). It implied that passing and higher admission scores got a high performance in LET than those who have a failed score in the admission exam. The data on college entrance scores as admission variables demonstrated that the greater the entrance score, the greater the probability of getting a higher performance on the teacher licensure examination (Gerundio & Balagtas, 2014).

Lastly, there was no significant difference between the civil status and type of school to the LET performance of the respondents with a p-value higher than 0.05 (0.354 and 0.303 respectively). This means that regardless of civil status and type of school they graduated there is no direct impact on the respondents' LET performance.

Table 4: Correlation Coefficients showing the relationship between the admission profile of respondents and the LET performance.

LET Performance	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value	Interpretation
Age	-.325	.000	Significant
CivilStatus	-.070	.354	Not Significant
FatherEdAttainment	-.054	.474	Not significant

MotherEdAttainment	-.052	.498	Not significant
Course	-.577	.000	Significant
TypeofSch	.078	.303	Not significant
EntrancExam	-.629	.000	Significant
GPA	-.504	.000	Significant

As reflected in Table 4, there is an indirect relationship to the respondents' profile such as age, course, Entrance Exam, and Grade point average with a respective r value of -.325, -.577, -.629, and .504 to the LET performance. Since the p-value of these admission profiles is less than 0.05, a significant relationship is implied, suggesting that those respondents with older age, married civil status, non-BSED course, and lower Grade point average are more likely to have a lower performance in teacher's Licensure Examination. Likewise, respondents with younger age, single civil status, and BSED Graduate and higher point grade average are more likely to have a higher performance in the LET.

Finally, the admittance respondents profile has an indirect and direct association are civil status, father and mother educational attainment, and type of school, with r values of -.070, -.054, -.053, and 0.078, respectively with the p-value of greater than 0.05 (0.354, 0.474, 0.498, and 0.303, respectively). It indicates that there is no significant relationship, implying that these admission profiles, regardless of civil status, parents' educational status, or type of school, have no bearing on their performance on the Teacher Licensure Examination.

Table 5: ANOVA Table of Predictors of LET Rating

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7052.383	8	881.548	28.621	.000 ^b
	Residual	5112.850	166	30.800		
	Total	12165.232	174			

a. Dependent Variable: PRCRating

b. Predictors: (Constant), EntranceExam, MotherEdAttainment, TypeofSch, CivilStatus, GPA, Course, Age, FatherEdAttainment

The ANOVA table indicated that at least one of the independent variables (Entrance Exam, Mother's Educational Attainment, Type of Sch, Civil Status, GPA, Course, Age, Father's Educational Attainment) is a predictor of performance in the teacher licensure examination, $F(8, 166) = 28.621, p = .000$. This applies that any of the variables mentioned have a big impact on passing the teacher licensure examination.

Table 6: Coefficient Table of LET Rating Predictors

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	98.556	3.148		31.307	.000
	Age	-.327	.809	-.024	-.404	.687
	CivilStatus	1.065	2.069	.028	.515	.607
	FatherEdAttainment	.701	.371	.118	1.891	.060
	MotherEdAttainment	-.776	.393	-.123	-1.976	.050

Course	-6.319	1.083	-.348	-5.832	.000
TypeofSch	1.072	1.193	.048	.898	.370
GPA	-4.013	.793	-.288	-5.058	.000
EntranceExam	-6.074	1.135	-.356	-5.351	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PRCRating

The coefficient table indicated that Mother's educational Attainment ($t = -1.976, p = .050$), Course ($t = -5.832, p = .000$), GPA ($t = -5.058, p = 0.000$), and Entrance Examination ($t = -5.351, p = .000$) are significant predictors in performance in LET performance. Here is the formula for predicting the LET performance of the respondents (LET Rating = $98.556 + -.327(A) + 1.065 (CS) + .701(FE) + -.766 (MEA) - 6.319 (Course) + 1.072 (TS) - 4.013 (GPA) - 6.074 (EE)$). As an illustration of the derived formula when a respondent age 15-17(1), civil status single (1), father and mother Ed. Attainment is elementary level (1), the course is non-BSED-graduate (2), with a GPA of 2.6 (4), passed the entrance exam (1) and graduated from public school (1), then his or her predicted LET rating will be 77.53%.

Table 7: Model Summary of LET Predictors

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.761 ^a	.580	.559	5.54980

a. Predictors: (Constant), EntranceExam, MotherEdAttainment, TypeofSch, CivilStatus, GPA, Course, Age, FatherEdAttainment

There 58% ($r^2 = .58$) of the variance in the results of the Licensure Examination is accounted for in the profile of respondents mentioned. Hence, about 42% could be attributed to other factors not investigated. Some research back up the predictive power of College Entrance scores and GWA on LET performance (Gerundio et.al, 2014; Montemayor, et al., 2009; Puertos, 2015; Tarun et al., 2014). For example, Puertos (2015) discovered a strong link between LET performance and pre-board ratings. Pre-board exams (Gerundio & Balagtas, 2014) and mock-board exams (Montemayor et al., 2009; Tarun et al., 2014) were found to significantly predict LET ratings. Furthermore, Nool et al. (2017) discovered that the three components of the college admission test, namely English language ability, verbal reasoning, and numerical ability, were predictors of graduates' LET performance. This calls for consideration as a requirement for incoming freshman education students in the coming years, so that only those with skills or a qualified profile are admitted to the program.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn from the findings:

1. LET takers have difficulty passing the specialization areas in the teachers' Licensure examination.
2. Education graduates perform better in General, Professional, and specialization, whereas non-education graduates performed poorly in the three areas.
3. High scholastic ratings and passing scores in the admission examination have a better performance in the teachers' Licensure examination compared to low scholastic ratings and non-passing scores in the admission examination.
4. There was a significant difference between the age, mothers' educational attainment, course, GPA, and admission score to the respondents' LET performance.
5. There was no significant difference between the civil status, educational attainment of the father, and school type to the LET performance of the respondents.

6. There was no significant difference between the civil status, educational attainment of the father, and school type to the LET performance of respondents.
7. There is an indirect significant relationship between the profile of the respondents such as age, course, Entrance Exam, and Grade point average.
8. Respondents with older age, married civil status, non-BSED course, and lower Grade point average are more likely to have a lower performance in Licensure Examination for teachers. Likewise, respondents with younger age, single civil status, and BSED Graduate and higher point grade average are more likely to have a higher performance in the Teachers Licensure Examination.
9. The Respondent's Mother's Educational Attainment, Course, GPA, and Entrance Examination are significant predictors in performance in LET performance.

Recommendations

Given the above-stated conclusions, the following recommendations are advanced;

1. It is suggested that the College of Education conduct review classes with a focus on the area of specialization.
2. It is recommended that the college strengthens the college-wide admission and retention policy by setting a standard score/grade in the admission and retention to be accepted/retained in the program.
3. It is recommended that Non-education graduates who desire to take education units should be given priority to be admitted to the college's post-undergraduate program and review classes in General, Professional, and Specialization.
4. For improved performance on the Licensure examination of Teachers, admission requirements must be strictly implemented including mothers' educational attainment, GPA, course, and Entrance exam score.
5. Future researchers should consider studying additional parameters that were not included in this study.

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